

Customer Tailoring Order Management system

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Abstract:- The project aims to automate the manually maintained tailoring industry. After automation, this will result in better services, accurate record-keeping, secure data, quick searches, and a paperless atmosphere. The project's primary focus has been on managing information for customers and decision-making. In order to provide security and authentication, each user of the system must log in using a username and password. The consumer can place an order and check the status of their dresses, and even provide feedback, after login. The system administrator has access to change records and handles customer data.

Keywords:- Tailoring Management System, Cloth Stitching, Tailor, Garments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Evolution of software is becoming increasingly crucial as successful software system age and become legacy systems. Software evolution has become a major focus of the software life cycle. Meanwhile, the software development process plays an important role in important software quality and speed. Software development projects benefit from well-designed processes, according to common belief, by improving their quality and productivity. It is important to understand that the phrase "Software Evolution process" refers to a group of connected software processes that are used when developing the software associated with the process.

There is no such thing as an identical project, and the same is true of identical processes. Software evolution methods must vary depending on the type of evolution, yet creating new software processes every time would be risky and expensive. They are frequently developed by customizing already-existing procedures and standards. As a result, we must modify the software evolution process using the patterns and standards that already exist.

The tailor shop management application allows you to all requests/deals, clients, salaries, prices, and estimates so you can keep calm and focus on other important things. In order to improve the management of tailoring activities inside the

company, an internet tailoring management system has been created. consumers will be able to measure accommodation for their tailors online, check the completion of their clothing items, and receive further assistance in record keeping.

The web-based tailoring administration system, which will also computerize the tailor shops and promote openness regardless of geographical regions, will solve all of these issues. Customers currently have to walk to the tailor shops to have their clothing measurements taken. Their complex traits are noted down on paper. Clients who want to check whether the items are finished must also get up from their desks.

This is expensive and laborious. Because manual systems are being employed, the overall process will typically be mild. Additionally, customers lack historical information regarding the cost of meshing their apparel.

Automate the manual tailoring system's flow while keeping the client and item databases accessible, information security is upheld, and client rights are respected. allowing consumers to send dimensions for their garments to be made by their tailors describing the cost, the texture type, the number of sets required, the urgency with which the client needs the dress done, and the type of material to be utilised to determine the overall cost depending on the material, amount, and length chosen, and to make money by selling that knowledge to the purchaser.

To improve report generation, it may provide customers with a report of completed garments for selection and scheduled appointments, and the head can view all of the clients and their orders.

II. RELATED WORK

Author[1] In this Paper Software of Tailoring is perfect for tailors and architects to handle the database of their customers and update their status regularly. Software is created in such a way that it makes all the processes easy for the customer as well as Tailors and also saves time. This software also helps to grow the business.

III. METHODS

Fig1. System Architecture

Both tailors and design architects can benefit from using tailoring software to manage a database of their clients' specifications, estimation techniques, installment schedules, and references from them. The client is informed of their desires and the status of their delivery by the tailoring application. It supports a wide range of languages. In order to stay organised, get a full report on your design firm, and focus on other vital things, Tailor Shop Management helps you manage all requests/deals, clients, salaries, prices, and estimations. It lets you keep track of client estimates and requests, let them know when work is finished, and let them have receipts made for them. It has a built-in schedule that allows you to keep track of the due date for a client's clothing.

When using tailoring software, you can log in as either an administrator or a tailor. An instrument for overseeing the company's tailoring operations is the internet tailoring management system. It will offer customers online help in the form of tailor estimating assistance, confirmation that their clothing is finished, and additional advice with correct record-keeping. By doing this, you can guarantee accurate data accessibility, data security, and simple storage, access, and recovery. The primary objective of the project is to develop a

computerized tailoring management system that is more effective and efficient than the existing manual system.

- Automate the present manual tailoring system and keep a searchable database of clients and products while upholding user rights and data security.
- To make it possible for customers to provide their measurements for custom clothing to their tailors.
- To give details on the price, the fabric type, the deadline by which the customer wants the dress completed, the kind of material to be used, and the required number of pairs.
- To calculate the entire cost based on the fabric choice, type of material, quantity, and duration and provide the buyer with that information.
- To enable the development of reports. The administrator can view all of the customers and their information, finished garments, and all of the bookings made, and it can provide a report of completed garments to the clients for pickup and bookings made.
- To construct a data bank that will make it simple to access or retrieve information about customers, orders, and users who have registered for the system.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig 2. Home page of Customer Tailoring Order Management System

Fig 3. About us page the of Customer Tailoring Order Management System

Fig 4. Admin login page of Customer Tailoring Order Management System

Fig 5. Customer Registration page of Customer Tailoring Order Management System

Fig 6. Customer login page of Customer Tailoring Order Management System

Fig 7. Tailor page of Customer Tailoring Order Management System

V. CONCLUSION

The process of intentionally or unintentionally adapting the software development approach has been used for decades. This procedure ensures that the development processes are changed depending on the specific task to be completed. Conflict still arises from the requirement to offer systems that would satisfy the particular requirements of every customer without interruption or disturbance. As stated in this study

paper, reliability engineering is offered as a viable remedy. The majority of enterprises engaged in software development adopt the spry development strategy and declaration, which guarantees and proposes emphases during development.

FUTURE SCOPE

Online tailoring is no doubt the future of the clothing or fashion industry. In today's world where everyone in their respective fields is concerned about sustainability, digital tailoring comes up with all new techniques completely governed by software. For sure it is going to rule the industry within the next few decades. Tailor Shop Management System will be an emerging step for small and medium-sized tailoring business that needs to manage customers, measurements, orders, and payments.

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